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Structural and functional characterization of proteins
and their modulation

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ABSTRACT

Surface functionalization of biodegradable polymeric materials using engineered adhesive–antimicrobial proteins

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Active packaging represents a promising strategy to enhance food safety, extend shelf life, and reduce reliance on synthetic preservatives. Within this framework, the MATE4MEAT project focuses on developing biodegradable packaging systems through the functionalization of sustainable polymeric materials with antimicrobial biomolecules. Biobased microbial polyesters, such as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs), were selected as renewable and fully biodegradable alternatives to conventional plastics [1].

In this study, engineered adhesive–antimicrobial chimeric proteins were developed to combine surface anchoring and biological activity within a single molecular system. These constructs combine an amphiphilic adhesive domain (HPB) [2] with antimicrobial peptides (AMPs), enabling the formation of stable and functional coatings at the food–polymer interface.

Two chimeric constructs were evaluated to investigate their ability to functionalize biopolymer materials. Additionally, preliminary combinatorial approaches involving the simultaneous application of multiple chimeras were explored to assess potential synergistic effects arising from their combined action.

Results demonstrated effective adhesion to biopolymer surfaces, modulation of surface wettability, and antimicrobial activity against target strains. Notably, both chimeras showed significant efficacy

in liquid and solid-phase assays, confirming their functional stability under different experimental conditions.

Overall, this work highlights adhesive–antimicrobial chimeras as a versatile platform for design active, bio-based packaging materials, enabling multifunctional coatings to reduce microbial contamination and improve the shelf life of red meat products.

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[1] P. Zytner, D. Kumar, A. Elsayed, A. Mohanty, B.V. Ramarao, M. Misra, *RSC sustainability* 1(9) (2023) 2120-2134.

[2] I. Stanzione, R. Pitocchi, A. Pennacchio, P. Cicatiello, A. Piscitelli, P. Giardina, *Frontiers in Molecular Biosciences* 9 (2022) 959166.

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